

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 21 APRIL-JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. JANETH L. LACOSTALES

Instructor I

Cebu Technological University – Barili Campus

janeth.lacostales@ctu.edu.ph

“THE HERO”

“Just in!” echoes the television in the living room. “A fire broke out in a restaurant in Bonifacio Global City (BGC) this afternoon. Thankfully, there were no casualties from the said accident since our beloved firefighters were very active to respond. Among those active responders was Mr. Randolph Cruz who bravely saved a seven-year-old boy who was caught up in the fire. Mr. Cruz bravely rescued the boy and successfully put him to safety. Those who witnessed the happening said Mr. Cruz was a real-life hero.”

Joana, Randolph’s wife, sighed as she turned off the TV. Then a young boy approached her, it was their son, Jason. He was holding a paper, it was a drawing of a man in a cape, scribbled beneath the drawing is, “My DAD is a hero.” At seven, Jason can draw beautiful pictures. This has been his way of expressing himself since he was born deaf and mute. Jason communicates in sign language and draws most of the time.

Joana knelt down, opened her arms wide, a gesture that they mutually understood. Jason approached his mother, the two wrapped themselves in a hug. Both of them miss their hero, they were wondering, “When will he come home?”

Forty-five minutes past eleven in the evening, Randolph came home. He gently opened the front door, carefully trying not to make any noise, afraid to wake his wife up. But when he turned the lights on, he startled, seeing Joana has been in the living room all along, wide awake, waiting for him.

“Do you know what time is it?” Joana asked.

Randolf replied, “Look, it has been a busy day at the station. You must have seen the news.”

Joana replied, now giving Randolph a stern look. “We saw it. You’re a hero.”

“Not now, Joana, please. I’m exhausted.” Randolph said in disgust.

Joana sighed and said, “Tomorrow is Jason’s school recognition. Don’t say you couldn’t come because you’re busy, you’ve always been busy. You have to make time for your son this time.”

“You know I can’t promise.” Randolph replied in a low voice, upset, but without a choice.

“Really? Well, think about this, hero. You have been there for other people; I think it’s time for you to be there for your son too.” Joana said as she walked out of the living room and went into Jason’s room.

This scenario has been going on in the family since the day Randolph got accepted in his job. He is a public servant and that is a good thing. But since then, he struggled to find time for his family.

The next day at the station, Randolph's phone rang for several times already. Eight missed calls. He couldn't answer his phone since he was in a meeting. Their team leader called for an emergency meeting since there is a threat of a possible earthquake in their area. Several earthquakes have already occurred in other cities and it is possible that their place will experience it too since a fault line has been recently discovered. Randolph checked his phone after the meeting and remembered about Jason's school recognition. He looked at the time. It's almost five o'clock. "I bet it's already done." He called his wife immediately.

After several ringing, Joana picked up the phone, "Hmm?"

"Look, we had an urgent meeting. I couldn't get myself excused—" Randolph answered frantically but Joana cut him off.

"That's it. We're going to mom and dad's place for some time." Joana said.

"You're not leaving me, are you?" Randolph asked.

Joana hanged up.

As soon as their conversation ended, the ground started to shake. Indeed, there was an earthquake!

Randolph shouted, "Drop! Cover! Hold!"

He started counting to twenty. If this shaking continues, he knows that he needs to get out of the room. Twenty-one, twenty-two, then he shouted, "This is bad! Everyone, get out! Get Out!"

Firefighters frantically ran outside the station, bending down, covering their heads. They went to an open space and waited for the shaking to stop. After eight more seconds, the shaking stopped. It was a magnitude 7.0 earthquake that lasted for thirty long seconds. As soon as the shaking stopped, everyone went back to their positions and had themselves ready for a rescue operation. Two big bridges, more than ten buildings, and over sixty houses destroyed. Randolph was panting, gasping. "My family. I need to save my family."

As a public servant, Randolph cannot leave just like that. So, he figured, he needed to save his family while saving others too. That is his job. Then, he called Joana.

She answered the phone, crying, "Ran, help us. I'm scared."

"How are you? Where are you?" Randolph asked.

"We're okay. We're at the bridge. At the middle of it. I think it's going to break in a few minutes. Jason's crying." Joana said in between sobs.

"Don't worry. I will go to you. I will save you." Randolph replied in courage.

The whole team rode the rescue truck. They went from block after block, rescuing injured kids, teens, adults, and seniors. After making sure that the patients were carefully attended, Randolph went to his team leader and asked if he could leave for his family. Without hesitation, the team leader permitted him to join the rescue team intended to go to the destroyed bridge. As soon as he got there, he frantically looked for his wife and son. With the lines now turned down, he couldn't contact them, but he was praying, hoping for the best. He was determined to save them.

At last, after much searching while helping others, he caught sight of his wife's car. It was hanging over the broken bridge, the car's about to fall down the river.

"Joana!" Randolph called to his wife.

Joana turned and saw her husband. Her eyes, welling with tears. "Jason fainted!"

“Hang in there! Don’t move! I’m coming to get you! Stay calm!” Randolph assured his wife.

He knew the car’s going to fall any minute now. If he doesn’t rush, he’ll surely lose his wife and son.

After careful planning, Ran and the team set up a net below the car, to have it secured in case it falls. Then he assigned a helicopter to rescue Joana and his son. While the helicopter spans on top of the car, Randolph shouted, “Joana, open the window! We have to get you out of the car, fast!”

Joana opened the window, now, the rescuers can see the unconscious Jason. Ran carefully tied a rope around his waist, preparing to go down and get his son. “Cruz, are you sure about this? We can ask someone to do this.” The team leader asked Randolph.

“Yes, sir. I need to save my family this time.” Ran replied as he pushed himself down. He carefully took Jason by his arms while giving Joana another set of rope. “Tie this around your waist!” After confirming that the rope is securely tied around Joana’s waist, Randolph signaled the team to pull them up. As soon as they set their feet in the helicopter, they witnessed the car falling from the bridge and into the net.

Randolf hugged his son and his wife. “You’re both safe now. Let’s get you to the hospital.”

The helicopter whirs to the hospital. Below are ambulance wailing, rescuers running, and people crying. Truly, in scenes of disasters, frontliners are real heroes, not just to every life that they save, but more so, to their families.

